

Journal of Social and Political Sciences

Deonandan, Raywat. (2019), Defining Poverty: A Summary of Competing Models. In: *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, Vol.2, No.1, 17-21.

ISSN 2615-3718

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1991.02.01.44

The online version of this article can be found at:

<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Social and Political Sciences* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of Social and Political Sciences, which includes, but not limited to, Anthropology, Government Studies, Political Sciences, Sociology, International Relations, Public Administration, History, Philosophy, Arts, Education, Linguistics, and Cultural Studies. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of Social and Political Sciences.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Defining Poverty: A Summary of Competing Models

Raywat Deonandan¹

¹ Interdisciplinary School of Health Sciences, University of Ottawa, Ottawa, Canada

Corresponding Author: Raywat Deonandan, University of Ottawa, 25 Universit Pvt, Ottawa, Canada K1N 6N5.
Tel: +16135625800 ext 8377. E-mail: rdeonand@uottawa.ca

Abstract

How we talk about poverty and low income is complicated by the competing methods for defining and measuring the phenomenon. In this article, I present a brief summary of the dominant methods currently in use by the governments of Canada and USA, and by the World Bank and large NGOs: absolute vs relative measures, low income cut-off (LICO), official poverty measure (OPM), global poverty line (GPL), human poverty index (HPI), and the multidimensional poverty index (MPI).

Keywords: Low Income, Poverty, Economic Deprivation, Millennium Development Goals

1. Background

Poverty and low income remain among the most hotly debated subjects in international development, and indeed in all discussions of economic development and governmental policy. In recent years, in the wake of the Millennium Development Goals, the world has had much to celebrate, with global poverty rates reported to have dropped to historic lows this year (Associated Press, 2018). And while the world continues to become less impoverished, the rate of change has slowed (World Bank, 2018). Despite global long-term improvements, local and short-term spikes in the number of people living lives of deprivation continue to cause concern, even in wealthy countries, like Canada and the USA.

A study (Angus Reid Institute, 2018), reported widely in Canadian news, showed that many Canadians are experiencing financial stress. A large proportion report needing to borrow money to buy groceries, eschewing dental care, and are experiencing hardship in ten other money-related scenarios presented to them. It is surprising, though, is that the study's estimate of the impoverished national fraction is considerably higher than the official governmental numbers. The study found that about 16% of the population is "struggling", while a further 11% is "on the edge" (i.e., at risk of struggling). This gives a total of 27% who are in some sort of financial jeopardy. Whereas, according to the official estimate, 4.9 million Canadians, or about 14% of the country, live beneath the line of indigence (Statistics Canada, 2018).

The difference between Angus Reid's and the government's estimates comes about because of the differences in philosophies and methodologies embraced by those doing the calculations. The Angus Reid Poverty Index (Angus Reid Institute, 2018b) is innovative and meaningful, but arises from a distinctly different set of

assumptions and definitions of poverty than does the Canadian government's official low-income cut-off line. The numbers are concerning and in need of policy attention, regardless of how they were manifested. But there is some educational utility in taking a moment to review the various philosophies underlying how poverty is conceptualized and measured.

Defining poverty and low income is important from a policy standpoint. Many governments use the designation to decide which communities receive special attention and resources. As a result, operationalizing any unspecific sense of deprivation can be a process fraught with unintentional bias.

About 21% of children in the USA live beneath the poverty line (National Center for Children in Poverty, 2018), while 10.2% of Danish children are thus beset (UNICEF, 2014). But do those statistics mean that Denmark is twice as wealthy as the USA? Is a poor person in Denmark as similarly deprived as a poor person in the USA? The confounding factor here is that different countries and organizations define the low-income cut-off line differently, making it difficult to compare across jurisdictions.

Some see poverty as strictly an economic state. Others see it as a condition of political vulnerability. Still others see it predominantly as a measure of social class. All of these interpretations are simultaneously correct and insufficient. The challenge is that we all have a sense in our minds of what a financially challenged existence looks like, but struggle to put that vision into a set of measurable indicators. Several competing measures have thus emerged, each telling only part of the story.

2. Relative vs Absolute Poverty

It is important to distinguish between "relative" and "absolute" poverty. A measure of relative poverty defines poverty as being below a threshold computed from within the population of interest. Someone who is "relatively impoverished" has significantly less wealth than other members of society. For example, a common practice is to define someone as poor if his or her income is less than 60% of the population's median income. This concept is sometimes called "economic distance." The advantage to this approach is that it ensures that poverty is understood in the context of its specific community.

The great disadvantage is that, regardless of actual levels of wealth, a relative measure necessitates that at least some members of the community are defined as impoverished. Imagine, for example, a nation of millionaires. It is a mathematical necessity that some of those millionaires will have an income less than 60% of the median. We would identify those people as impoverished -- even though they are millionaires.

"Absolute" poverty, on the other hand, is a level of poverty defined in terms of the minimal requirements necessary to afford a basic standard of living. The inability to achieve that minimal standard is considered to be experiencing deprivation and therefore poverty. To compute absolute poverty, we define a set of necessities that we place in our grocery basket. We can therefore call this a "market basket measure" (MBM). In Canada, the official MBM includes the costs of food, clothing, footwear, transportation, shelter and other expenses (Statistics Canada, 2015) for a reference family of two adults and two children, adjusted for geographical region. According to Canada's MBM, a Torontonian from a 4-person family earning less than \$40,595 would be low-income in 2015 (Statistics Canada, 2017).

On the other hand, one of the "relative poverty" thresholds commonly used in this country is the Low-Income Measure (LIM), which is the median income of the population, adjusted for household size. Based on 2015 numbers, a Canadian in a four-person household is considered low-income (Statistics Canada, 2017b) if he or she makes less than \$44,266 after taxes. Unfortunately, then, the LIM and MBM give different threshold estimates for the same person.

3. Low Income Cut-off

Statistics Canada also uses something called a Low-Income Cut-off (LICO), which is an income threshold below which a family will likely devote a larger share of its income to the necessities of food, shelter, and clothing than an average family would. For various family sizes and community sizes, data are collected about how much income families typically retain after paying taxes, and about how much of that income they spend on food, shelter, clothing, and the other necessities of life. The income value associated with 20 percentage points above the average expenditure is defined as the LICO for that particular family and community size. (Statistics Canada, 2015b). The LICO really hasn't been updated since 1992 except to adjust for inflation.

4. U.S. Official Poverty Measure

The United States Census Bureau determines poverty status by comparing pre-tax cash income against a threshold that is set at three times the cost of a minimum food diet. This is called the "Official Poverty Measure", or OPM, and was first devised in 1963, with the cost of food is updated each year to reflect inflation. The OPM varies by family size, with the definition of family rigidly prescribed. In 2017, the OPM poverty threshold for a family of four was \$30,750, or about 13% of Americans (Wissman, 2017).

The Supplemental Poverty Measure (SPM) was introduced in 2010 in the USA to account for the criticisms of the OPM. Rather than focusing just on food expenditures, the SPM attempts to capture what Americans expend on all basic necessities: food, clothing, shelter, and utilities. It also accounts for taxes paid and government benefits received. According to the SPM, about 14% of Americans live beneath the poverty line (Center for Poverty Research, 2018). But the OPM is still the official measure.

5. Global Poverty Line

Perhaps the most commonly applied poverty threshold, used since 1990, is the so-called global poverty line (GPL), which is delineated by the World Bank. The line is based solely on the cost of living, and is assessed by computing the global prices of key commodities. Up until 2008, the GPL was conveniently defined as one U.S. dollar per day. Anyone making less than this amount was said to be unable to purchase the necessities of life and was thus impoverished. In 2015, due to global changes in commodity prices, that line was redefined as \$1.90 per day (World Bank, 2015).

6. Human Poverty Index

From 1997 until fairly recently, the United Nations relied upon an indicator called the Human Poverty Index (HPI). It is a mathematical combination of scores that describe a population's longevity, literacy, and standard of living. And the formula is different for poor countries versus wealthy countries. For poor countries, less longevity is expected, while the standard of living is based on very basic conditions, such as whether treated water is available and whether children tend to be underweight. For wealthy countries, the formula includes a measure of social exclusion, typically estimated from the nation's unemployment rate.

7. Multidimensional Poverty Index

There are ongoing efforts to produce more comprehensive and thorough poverty estimators. Among the more impactful of recent innovations is the Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI), which was developed in 2010 by the Oxford Poverty & Human Development Initiative, and which has replaced the HPI in most serious international comparisons of poverty. The MPI is intended to measure acute poverty in terms of both the proportion of experiencing multiple deprivations *and* the intensity of such deprivations (Oxford Poverty & Human Development Initiative, 2011). It does so by measuring individuals' experiences with health, education, and standard of living (via traditional development indicators, like the availability of clean drinking water, and whether the home has a proper floor), and summing those experiences across the measured population.

The MPI is usually only computed for low income countries. In 2016, computations were completed for 102 countries, which accounts for about 75% of the total human population. From those data, 1.6 billion people were

found to be multidimensionally poor (compared with 1.3 billion who live beneath the Global Poverty Line). According to the MPI, the poorest country in the world is Niger, whose 2012 MPI estimate is 0.605. In second place is Ethiopia, whose 2011 data results in an estimate of 0.564.

The MPI method is a bit more inclusive than other methods, since it accounts for impoverishing factors beyond the cost of goods.

8. Conclusion

Clearly, there is a multitude of methods for measuring financial distress, each rife with its own strengths, biases and values. Do we only care about whether a poor person survives, or do we also care whether he thrives? Are food and shelter the only baseline requirements, or should we include access to services –health, legal, financial– or even access to information and electronic connectivity? The challenge when discussing low-income and deprivation is to select the most appropriate measure for the story being told, and to avoid comparing computations that were derived from dissimilar assumptions, values, and intents.

References

- Angus Reid Institute. What does poverty look like in Canada? July 17, 2018. Available at: <http://angusreid.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/2018.06.21-poverty.pdf>
- Angus Reid Institute. Poverty index. 2018. Available at: <http://angusreid.org/ari-poverty-index/>
- Associated Press. Global poverty rate drops to record low 10%: World Bank. CNBC. Sep 19, 2018. Available at: <https://www.cnbc.com/2018/09/19/world-bank-global-poverty-rate-drops-to-record-low.html>
- Center for Poverty Research. What is the current poverty rate in the United States? Last accessed Dec 20, 2018. Available at: <https://poverty.ucdavis.edu/faq/what-current-poverty-rate-united-states>
- National Center for Children in Poverty. Child Poverty. 2018. Available at: <http://www.nccp.org/topics/childpoverty.html>
- Oxford Poverty & Human Development Initiative. Training Material for Producing National Human Development Reports. Oct, 2011. Available at: <http://www.ophi.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/MPI-Primer.pdf>
- Statistics Canada. Before-tax and after-tax low income status (census family LIM) by family type and family composition. Dec 20, 2018. Available at: <https://www150.statcan.gc.ca/t1/tb11/en/tv.action?pid=1110001501>
- Statistics Canada. Market Basket Measure (MBM) thresholds for economic families and persons not in economic families, 2015. Aug 24, 2017. Available at: https://www12.statcan.gc.ca/census-recensement/2016/ref/dict/tab/t4_5-eng.cfm
- Statistics Canada. Low-income measures thresholds (LIM-AT and LIM-BT) for private households of Canada, 2015. Aug 10, 2017b. Available at: https://www12.statcan.gc.ca/census-recensement/2016/ref/dict/tab/t4_2-eng.cfm
- Statistics Canada. Market Basket Measure (2011 base). Nov 27, 2015. Available at: <https://www150.statcan.gc.ca/n1/pub/75f0002m/2013002/mbm-mpc-eng.htm>
- Statistics Canada. Calculation of an after-tax low income cut-off. Nov 27, 2015b. Available at: <https://www150.statcan.gc.ca/n1/pub/75f0002m/2012002/figure/fig1-eng.htm>
- UNICEF. Children of the Recession: The impact of the economic crisis on child well-being in rich countries. 2014. Available at: <https://www.unicef-irc.org/publications/pdf/rc12-eng-web.pdf>
- Wissman L. 2017 Federal Poverty Level Guidelines. People Keep. Feb 7, 2017. Available at: <https://www.peoplekeep.com/blog/2017-federal-poverty-level-guidelines>
- World Bank. Decline of Global Extreme Poverty Continues but Has Slowed: World Bank. Sep 19, 2018. Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2018/09/19/decline-of-global-extreme-poverty-continues-but-has-slowed-world-bank>
- World Bank. FAQs: Global Poverty Line Update. Sep 30, 2015. Available at: <http://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/poverty/brief/global-poverty-line-faq>

Copyrights

Copyright for this article is retained by the author(s), with first publication rights granted to the journal.

This is an open-access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>).